

Induced and Photochemical Oxidation of Sodium Tartrate by Air and its Use in Diabetes and Prolonged Fasting.

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In several publications (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, **29**, 926; 1928, **32**, 1263; 1930, **34**, 711, 993; 1932, **36**, 2504; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, **191**, 150) we have shown that in presence of inductors like ferrous hydroxide, cerous hydroxide, manganous hydroxide, glutathione, insulin, etc., which can take up oxygen directly from air under ordinary condition, solutions or suspensions of food materials like starch, sugars, proteins (egg-yellow, egg-white, milk, amino acids etc.), fats (butter, lecithin, etc.), glycogen and glycerol can be readily oxidised by passing air at the ordinary temperature. Moreover, it has been shown that solutions or suspensions of these food materials can be oxidised to carbon dioxide and water by simply passing air in presence of sunlight. In presence of sunlight, the induced oxidation of food materials is greatly increased.

In this paper, we are recording the experimental results obtained in the oxidation of sodium tartrate in presence of inductors like ferrous hydroxide or cerous hydroxide by passing air through its solutions and also the results obtained in presence of alkali, alkali carbonate, alkali bicarbonate and alkali sulphite respectively in (i) diffused light and (ii) sunlight.

In these experiments, a slow current of air, free from carbon dioxide, is passed through a bottle containing the solution of sodium tartrate. Each of these bottles contained freshly prepared 0.1069 g. of cerous hydroxide or 0.06476 g. of ferrous hydroxide. In each case 10 c.c. of the tartrate solution are added to the inductor and the total volume is then made up to 100 c.c. and a known volume of air was allowed to bubble slowly through the mixture. After passing the requisite amount of air the mixture is treated with a saturated solution of potassium sulphate to coagulate the hydroxide, filtered and washed with water containing potassium sulphate till free from tartrate. The filtrate containing the unoxidised tartrate is concentrated to a small volume (10 c.c.) and heated with 5 g. of potassium

chloride and 5 c.c. of glacial acetic acid (99—100%). The tartrate is then precipitated as bitartrate by the addition of 50-60 c.c. of absolute alcohol. The precipitate of potassium bitartrate is allowed to settle for 2 hours and filtered and washed well with absolute alcohol free from acid. The precipitate is dissolved in hot water and the solution is titrated with a standard solution of caustic soda, using phenolphthalein as indicator. From the amount of alkali required, the quantity of tartrate remaining unoxidised is estimated. The following are the experimental results.

TABLE I.

In each of these experiments, 0.06476 g. ferrous hydroxide or 0.1069 g. cerous hydroxide was taken. 1 C.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH = 0.0194 g. of Na-tartrate. 10 c.c. of solution of Na-tartrate = 5.1 c. c. of $N/10$ -NaOH = $5.1 \times 0.0194 = 0.0989$ g. of Na-tartrate.

Inductor.	Vol. of air passed.	Duration of air passed.	Amt. of Na-tart. left after the expt. in terms of $N/10$ -NaOH.	Amt. of Na-tart. oxidised in terms of $N/10$ -NaOH.	Na-tart. oxidised.
Cerous hydroxide	36.5 litre	13 hr.	2.95 c.c.	2.15 c.c.	42.15%
	73.0	30	2.10	3.00	58.8
Ferrous hydroxide	36.5	13	3.95	1.15	22.03
	73.0	30	3.20	1.90	37.3

From the results in Table I, it is seen that the amount of sodium tartrate oxidised is greater with cerous hydroxide than with ferrous hydroxide used as inductor and that the amount of oxidation increases with the increase of volume of air which is passed through the mixture.

In order to find out whether cupric hydroxide when added in varying amounts to the inductors, would accelerate or retard the oxidation of sodium tartrate, we have carried on some experiments by adding 5 c.c. of copper sulphate solution of varying concentrations to solutions of ferrous sulphate or cerous chloride and the mixture precipitated as hydroxides by the addition of an equivalent amount of caustic soda. These mixed hydroxides are then used as

inductors in the oxidation of sodium tartrate. The following are the experimental results.

TABLE II.

In each of these experiments, 20 c.c. of $\text{FeSO}_4 \equiv 0.06476$ g. $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ or $\text{CeCl}_2 \equiv 0.1069$ g. $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_3$ were taken to which 5 c.c. of CuSO_4 were added and then precipitated as hydroxides by the addition of equivalent amount of alkali. 10 C.c. of Na-tartrate soln. = 5.1 c.c. of $N/10\text{-NaOH}$.

Inductor.	Vol. of air passed.	Duration of air passed.	Amt. of CuSO_4 added in 5 c.c. of the soln. added.	Amt. of Na-tart. left after the expt. in terms of $N/10$ NaOH ,	Amt. of Na-tart. oxidised in terms of $N/10$ NaOH .	Na-tartrate oxidised.
$\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$	36.5 litre	13 hr.	0.05 g.	3.5 c.c.	1.6 c.c.	31.37%
	"	"	0.025	2.7	2.4	47.06
	73.0	30	0.0025	1.7	3.4	66.7
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$	36.5	13	0.05	4.2	0.9	17.6
	"	"	0.025	3.5	1.6	31.4
	73.0	30	0.0025	2.6	2.5	49.02

From Table II, we find that the amount of oxidation of sodium tartrate is greatly accelerated by the addition of very small quantity of copper. On comparing the results given in Tables I and II it is seen that copper, when present in greater quantity acts as a marked retarder, whilst it acts as an accelerator when present in minute quantity. We have also investigated the influence of mild and strong alkali on the oxidation of sodium tartrate without any inductor in presence or absence of sunlight. The following results are obtained.

TABLE III.

Experiments in diffused light.

In each of these experiments, 10 c.c. of sodium tartrate solution were taken to which a definite weight of strong or mild alkali was added and air was passed into the solution. The volume of air passed = 20 litres in 7 hours. 10 C.c. of sodium tartrate solution =

5.1 c.c. of N/10-NaOH.

Substance used.	Amt. of substance added in 10 c.c. of the soln.	Amt. of Na-tart. left after the expt. in terms of N/10-NaOH.	Amt. of Na tart. oxidised in terms of N/10-NaOH.	Na-tart. oxidised.
1. Caustic soda	0.04 g.	4.85 c.c.	0.25 c.c.	4.9%
2. Sodium carbonate	0.10	4.90	0.20	3.92
3. Sodium bicarbonate	0.10	4.95	0.15	2.94
4. Sodium sulphite	0.10	4.80	0.30	5.9

TABLE IV.

Experiments in presence of sunlight.

10 C.c. of solution of sodium tartrate = 5.1 c.c. of N/10-NaOH.

Volume of air passed = 20 litres in 7 hours.

Substance used.	Amt. of substance added in 10 c.c. of the soln.	Amt. of Na-tart. left after the expt. in terms of N/10-NaOH.	Amt. of Na tart. oxidised in terms of N/10-NaOH.	Na-tart. oxidised.
1. Caustic soda	0.04 g.	4.1 c.c.	1.0 c.c.	19.6%
2. Sodium carbonate	0.10	4.2	0.9	17.6
3. Sodium bicarbonate	0.10	4.3	0.8	15.6
4. Sodium sulphite	0.10	3.8	1.3	25.5

The above results (Tables III and IV) show that the amount of oxidation of sodium tartrate is greater in presence of sunlight than that in its absence under the same conditions. The order of oxidation of sodium tartrate in presence of alkali or alkali salts in both the cases is the following:—sodium sulphite > sodium hydroxide > sodium carbonate > sodium bicarbonate

Sodium sulphite acts also as an inductor and that is why the amount of oxidation is greatest in its presence. The foregoing results obtained in light show that in presence of sunlight the amount of tartrate oxidised is greater than in the diffused light of the laboratory. It is known that visible light, specially rays of longer wave-lengths, can penetrate the epidermis to appreciable depths and

hence it has been suggested that light acts as a preventive and curative agent in diseases by acting not only as a stimulant of the body cells but also as an accelerator in the metabolism of food materials (compare Dhar, "New Conceptions in Biochemistry," 1932).

From these results, it appears that tartrates are oxidised both in presence of light or inductors. Hence it seems that in the animal body tartrates may act not only as buffers in maintaining the alkalinity of the system but they can also supply energy acting as food material.

TABLE Va.

Estimation of potassium oleate oxidised by the addition of small quantity of inductors—ferrous ($\equiv 0.00648$ g.) or cerous hydroxide ($\equiv 0.01069$ g.)—in presence or absence of sodium tartrate.

To each of these hydroxides 20 c.c. of 1% solution of potassium oleate added. The volume of air passed = 73 litres in 30 hrs. 20 C.c. of sodium tartrate solution = 10.3 c.c. of *N*/10-caustic soda = 0.1998 g. of sodium tartrate.

Amount of absorption of I Cl_3 by fat in terms of *N*/10-sodium thiosulphate before the experiments (blank) = 11.3 c.c.

Inductor.	Amt. of Na-tartrate added.	Amt. of absorption of I Cl_3 by fat left after the expt. terms in <i>N</i> /10-thio.	Amt. of fat oxidised in terms of <i>N</i> /10-thio.	Amount of fat oxidised.
Cerrous hydroxide	0.0000 g.	6.2 c.c.	5.1 c.c.	45.1%
	0.1998	9.4	1.9	16.8
Ferrous hydroxide	0.0000	6.7	4.6	40.7
	0.1998	10.4	0.9	7.9

TABLE Vb.

Estimation of sodium tartrate oxidised by the addition of small quantity of inductors under identical conditions as in Table Va in presence or absence of potassium oleate.

Amount of sodium tartrate taken in 20 c.c. of the solution before experiment in terms of *N*/10 caustic soda (blank) = 10.3 c.c.

Inductor.	Amt. of K-oleate added.	Amt. of Na-tart. left after the expt. in terms of N/10-NaOH.	Amt. of Na-tart oxidised in terms of N/10-NaOH.	Na-tart. oxidised.
Cerrous hydroxide	Nil	6.7 c.c.	3.6 c.c.	34.95%
	20 c.c.	8.6	1.7	16.5
Ferrous hydroxide	Nil	8.2	2.1	20.3
	20	8.8	1.5	14.6

The experimental results show that by the addition of sodium tartrate, the amount of potassium oleate oxidised in 30 hours by 73 litres of air is considerably decreased. In the case of ferrous hydroxide as inductor, in presence of sodium tartrate the percentage of potassium oleate oxidised is 7.9, whilst under identical conditions and in absence of sodium tartrate, the percentage is 40.7. The corresponding results with cerous hydroxide as inductor are 16.8% and 45.1% respectively. Hence it is clear that the addition of a tartrate markedly decreases the velocity of the oxidation of potassium oleate. Moreover, the presence of oleate retards the velocity of the oxidation of sodium tartrate.

These results seem important from the point of view of treatment of diabetes and prolonged fasting. Under normal conditions, the heat and energy of the body are derived from the simultaneous combustion of carbohydrates, fats and possibly of proteins. When, as a result of special conditions, such as diabetes, carbohydrate is not burning, more fat and possibly protein must be burnt in order to maintain the body temperature and activity at its normal level. Hence in unit time, more fat would be burning than under normal conditions, and the combustion of fat would be incomplete, so that acetone bodies would be formed. Chakravarti and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 617) have observed that in the rapid oxidation of fatty acids by hydrogen peroxide and ferric salts, there is a formation of acetone bodies. They have also observed that if the rate of oxidation of fats be slowed down, as the case when carbohydrates (*e.g.*, glucose) are present, the amount of acetone bodies formed diminishes. Palit and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 710) further find that, in the slow and induced oxidation of fats, acetone bodies are not formed at all, but only carbon dioxide and water, the products of normal metabolism.

The experimental results recorded here and in previous publications show that just as carbohydrates decrease the velocity of oxidation of the fats, similarly tartrates can also decrease the velocity of the oxidation of fat. Hence a tartrate or a citrate, apart from its power of acting as a buffer in removing the excessive hydrogen ion (H°) generated in the body, may serve as an anti-ketogenic substance like a carbohydrate.

The authors are of opinion that the tartrates or citrates in the drinks will prove beneficial in the treatment of long continued fasts, because in such cases the body has not lost the power of oxidation and will utilise the tartrates and citrates as food along with the fats of the body.

Our experimental results show that in presence of traces of copper, the induced oxidation of tartrate is markedly facilitated, whilst in larger concentrations, it retards the same process. Hence it appears that in the treatment of metabolism diseases or anaemia, the addition of traces of copper salts to iron or manganese may be useful.

SUMMARY.

1. Sodium tartrate is oxidised by air in presence of inductors like ferrous hydroxide or cerous hydroxide and the amount of oxidation is greater with cerous hydroxide than with ferrous hydroxide. The amount of oxidation increases with the amount of air passed.

2. It has been found that copper salts when present in minute quantity accelerate the induced oxidation of sodium tartrate but when present in larger quantity they act as retarders.

3. Sodium tartrate can be oxidised both in presence or absence of sunlight by passing air through its solution when mixed with strong or mild alkali. The amount of oxidation is greater in light than in its absence.

4. Light in the treatment of disease, is likely to act as a stimulant of body cells and accelerator of metabolism.

5. The experimental results show that tartrates may act not only as buffers in maintaining the alkalinity of the system but can also supply energy serving as food material.

6. It is suggested that a mixture of sodium tartarate or citrate and sodium bicarbonate is likely to be more efficacious in the treatment of diabetes and long continued fasting than sodium bicarbonate alone.

